

Studies in Diphenyl Series. Part II. A New Method of the Synthesis of 9-Hydroxyphenanthrene.

BY NRIPENDRANATH CHATTERJEE.

From the point of view of constitution, phenanthrene is intimately related to naphthalene on the one hand and diphenyl on the other, so phenanthrene or its derivatives may be synthesised from the derivatives of both.

Confining our attention to the syntheses in which the starting materials are derivatives of diphenyl it may be observed that the methods available so far are of limited scopes (*cf.* Graebe and Aubin, *Annalen*, 1888, **247**, 257; Libermann, *Ber.*, 1911, **44**, 1453; Kenner and Turner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, **99**, 2101).

The method described in the present investigation is one capable of considerable extension. The starting material is *oo'*-diphenic acid or a derivative of the substance. *o-o'*-Diphenic acid is converted to the anhydride (I) by acetyl chloride and reduced by sodium amalgam (5%). The lactone of 2'-oxymethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (II) which is formed is heated with KCN at 180°-190° for 3 to 4 hours when due to the ring opening, the potassium salt of 2-cyanomethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (III) is obtained. The above compound when boiled with 30% KOH yields 2-carboxymethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (IV). It is converted to the corresponding calcium salt which on dry distillation yields 9-hydroxyphenanthrene (V). From the reaction product the compound is isolated by extracting with alcohol and precipitating it as the picrate.

In practice one of the greatest difficulties to be encountered is with respect to the properties of the lactone. The yield of the lactone is not satisfactory, since due to a secondary reaction the anhydride itself is converted into diphenic acid and its mono ester. But this does not in any way interfere with the processes involved. The acid, thus produced, as well as the mono ester (after its hydrolysis) can be used over and over again, and there is little loss of material.

With substituted *oo'*-diphenic acids, the corresponding phenanthrene derivatives may be obtained and there will be no ambiguity due to the orientation of the various groups.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Lactone of 2-hydroxymethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (II).—Sodium amalgam (5%) was added in portions during 24 hours to a solution of diphenic anhydride (40 g.) in alcohol (100 c. c.) which was mechanically stirred. The solution was kept acidic by means of dilute sulphuric acid (excess of acid must be avoided, otherwise too much of ester will be formed). The solution was made alkaline and the sodium sulphate was filtered and the alkaline filtrate after dilution was

a solution of the free acid, the mono acid ester and the lactone and they were separated thus: (i) Fractional precipitation by the addition of regulated quantities of acid. (ii) Extraction with dilute NaHCO_3 solution which dissolves most of the mono ester. (iii) Fractional crystallisation from ethereal solution. It has been thus possible to obtain the pure lactone free from the acid and the mono-ester. It crystallises from benzene in needles, m.p. 136° , yield 5-6%. This lactone has been prepared by Kenner and Turner, (*loc. cit.*) (Found: C, 79.9; H, 4.7. Calc. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$: C, 80.0; H, 4.7 per cent).

2'-Cyanomethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (III).—The lactone (0.5 g.) was well mixed with potassium cyanide (E.P, 0.3g.) and heated in a test tube in an oil-bath for 3 to 4 hours. The resulting dark coloured cold mass was digested with water and the insoluble portion removed by extraction with ether. The aqueous layer was filtered and on acidification the free acid was precipitated. It crystallises from benzene in light brown needles, m. p. 240° . (Found: N, 5.7. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires N, 5.9 per cent).

2'-Carboxymethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl (IV).—*2'-Cyanomethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl* was dissolved in 30% caustic potash solution and allowed to boil till no more ammonia was evolved. It was then filtered and acidified, when *2'-carboxymethyl-2-carboxydiphenyl* separated, m. p. 295° . (Found: C, 70.0; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_9$ requires C, 70.3; H, 4.6 per cent).

9-Hydroxyphenanthrene (V).—The calcium salt of (IV) was placed in a small pyrex retort glass to the stem of which was attached a wide mouth test tube with a side tube which can be connected to a vacuum pump. The bulb was now rapidly heated when a yellow oil condensed in the test tube. The distillate was dissolved in alcohol and on addition of a saturated solution of picric acid a red coloured picrate was precipitated. It was filtered, washed and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 185° . *9-Hydroxyphenanthrene*, regenerated from the pure picrate, melts at 153° .

In conclusion, the author desires to express his thanks to Professor Dr. P. C. Mitter for much encouragement and advice during the course of this work.